

Emily V. Ho, Chengxian Shi, Jessica Cassin, Michelle Y. He, Ryan D. Nguyen, Genevieve E. Ryan, Karen J. Tonsfeldt, Pamela L. Mellon. Reproductive Deficits Induced by Prenatal Anti-Mullerian Hormone Exposure Require Androgen Receptor in Kisspeptin Cells. *Endocrinology*, 2021

Supplemental Figures

Supplemental Figure 1: pAMH did not increase body weight throughout the lifespan of F₁ or F₂ offspring with or without KARKO.

Body weight measurements at various ages in VEH and pAMH. (a) F₁ females (Treatment x Age, $F_{7,243} = 1.729$, $p = 0.1029$), (b) F₁ males (Treatment x Age, $F_{6,190} = 1.290$, $p = 0.2638$), (c) F₂ females (Treatment x Age, $F_{4,111} = 1.374$, $p = 0.2476$), (d) F₂ males (Treatment x Age, $F_{2,149} = 1.729$, $p = 0.1366$), (e) KARKO and Ctrl F₁ females (Treatment x Age, $F_{12,250} = 1.537$, $p = 0.1113$), and (f) KARKO and Ctrl F₁ males (Treatment x Age, $F_{12,244} = 1.656$, $p = 0.1130$). Data were analyzed using Mixed-effects model with the Geisser-Greenhouse correction to account for differing variability of differences.

Supplemental Figure 2: Kiss1 and Ar expression in the ovary.

RNAScope was used for *in situ* hybridization in ovary to detect Ar and Kiss1. 10X image shows dispersed *Kiss1* expression (green), while *Ar* (magenta) has robust expression in the developing follicles. Inset (i) shows *Kiss1* cells without clear *Ar* colocalization near but not inside an antral follicle. Inset (ii) shows *Kiss1* cells with clear *Ar* colocalization distal from antral follicles.

Supplemental Figure 3: Kiss1 and Ar expression in the testis.

RNAScope was used for *in situ* hybridization in testis to detect Ar and Kiss1. 10X image shows very few cells with *Kiss1* signal (green), and dense *Ar* (magenta). Inset shows three example *Kiss1* cells that co-express *Ar*.

Supplemental Files

Source image files for Supplemental Figure 2 and 3. .nd2 files can be accessed with FIJI or Nikon Elements software.

Channel 1: *Kiss1*, FITC

Channel 2: *Ar*, Cy5

Files:

Ovary 10X.nd2

Ovary 40X.nd2

Testis 10X.nd2

Testis 40X.nd2

Figure 1

(a) F₁ pAMH Female Offspring

(b) F₁ pAMH Male Offspring

(c) F₂ pAMH Female Offspring

(d) F₂ pAMH Male Offspring

(e) KARKO F₁ pAMH Female Offspring

(f) KARKO F₁ pAMH Male Offspring

Figure 2

Figure 3

